

A Comparison of Reading, Writing, and Speaking on the Link Between Sociolinguistics and Linguistics

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to use the concept on which Sociolinguistics and applied linguistics are based on determining Communities of Practice. In keeping with Chomsky's definition, Lyons (1970) defines a "true" speech community as "all people who use a particular language (or dialect)". Hockett (1958), on the other hand, provides a broader perspective by defining a speech community as "an entire group of people who communicate with each other directly or indirectly through a common language". The stricter definition proposed by Lyon was criticized on the grounds that "if speech communities are defined solely by their linguistic characteristics, we must recognize the inherent circularity of any such definition as a common property in that language itself." This criticism is since language itself is a social property (Wardhaugh). Wardhaugh's views are less in conflict with Hockett's, since Hockett leaves open the classification as to what qualifies as "an entire group of people", since "a social group" qualifies as strictly "an entire group of people". Wardhaugh's views are less inconsistent with Hockett's, as Hockett leaves open the classification of what qualifies as a "whole group of people." The challenge is to determine exactly what constitutes a "social group" or "a complete collection of individuals". Wardhaugh (p. 119) disagrees with Hudson's (1996) view that the concept of speech community is easy to use without any difficulty: *they like to think subjectively in terms of communities or social types*. Also, since any individual can belong to more than one speech community, no single individual defines and is not defined by his or her speech community.

Keywords: *Sociolinguistics, Linguistics, Reading, Writing, Speaking*

Introduction

It is generally accepted that "a group is a difficult term to define", making "conversation community" a "highly abstract concept" (Wardhaugh). At this point, the creation of communities

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of practice can provide some benefits, especially in terms of formulating, defining and implementing standards.

A group of individuals who share an interest or love for what they do and learn how to do it better as they interact with each other frequently, argue that, while a general statement, space, community, and practice are the most crucial factors in determining the boundaries of a community of practice. Members come together because they have a common learning need (area); Over time, this collective learning becomes a link within the community, and members' interactions provide resources that influence how they behave (practice).

Standards are influenced by the language used in society, which in turn is shaped by the culture, procedures and activities they carry out. It is important to consider whether the people responsible for the development of any standard can be considered an accurate reflection of the community for which the standard is intended. It is important to determine the scope of the community served, so care should be taken in this regard.

That everyone communicates in the same human language they communicate in the same functional language (target speech community, app community or domain language) and they all belong to the same Community of Apps because everyone uses the same human language. This is one of the missing components in the standard process, which includes the formulation of standards, the evaluation of a standard's fitness for use, and the final implementation of the standards.

linguistic diversity is not formally included in the standards process, and to the implications and misunderstandings that arise as a direct result of this fact, and to discuss the advantages of providing an applied linguistic component. It is also important to formally involve communities of practice as a binding mechanism in the standards process, more specifically.

Applied Linguistics and Societies of Practice

Standards are well-defined responses to specific situations. It is designed to provide uniformity and consistency in environments where variability can occur. However, due to its designation as a "standard", the specific problem the standard was developed to solve is often overlooked or ignored in efforts to extend the standard's implementation and use beyond the community and use

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case. Ironically, this goes against exactly what a standard should be. The most obvious manifestation of this problem is seen in data, communication and interoperability centered standards. The absence of arbitrariness in physical elements reduces the likelihood of misapplication of a physical standard, such as some kind of screw; however, this scenario is still possible. The design of the screw threads determines how the screw will perform in a variety of materials, such as wood or metal, and requires less interpretation than other designs. It is possible to "misuse" a screw designed for wood in metal, but the mismatch will be obvious due to the physical appearance of the screw.

On the other hand, language becomes the most crucial factor when considering data, message and associated interoperability standards. These are, by definition, types of standards that focus on communication using language. Additionally, widespread implementation is almost always a priority given the amount of work that has gone into developing standards.

The paradox of language is that although it was created to facilitate communication, language is in a constant state of change and development, making it difficult to communicate directly due to misunderstandings. Changes in language, such as dialects and jargon, can lead to improvements in interpersonal communication within a single community. On the other hand, this will cause the language to become more prominent from the communities to which it belongs. Just as language can be seen and functioned as an expression of a particular community, so can standards. Standards make it possible to achieve better results in the context of a particular community and use case. However, this refinement is lost in the implementation phase of the project when a standard is enforced as a single language solution for all groups within a social system.

This is largely attributable to the lack of clear definitions of the Community of Practice (or 'domain') for which any standard has been produced. The Community of Practice is not fully defined when a standard is formulated, as the community or domain is assumed or inferred based on the structure of the organization and the participants that make up the standard. The reason for this is the structure of the organization and the participants who set the standard. In fact, the group that developed the standard is self-selecting and believes it applies to a wider audience. To define

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the target audience, general expressions open to many interpretations were used. The terms "financial services", "teachers" and "doctors" are just a few examples.

Although these categories may not seem problematic at first glance, it can be said that the term "teacher" may apply to primary school teachers or university professors. In addition, the education levels covered by the concept of "primary education educator" can be questioned. It should be clear that the requirements for 'teachers' regarding higher education levels would probably not be acceptable for primary school and vice versa. This is something to be understood.

Methodology

In some cases, standardization is the result of a community's attempt to gain legitimacy for deviations from existing practices or their use of standardization as a tool of force. This is like how language standardization has been used throughout history, whether it was the imposition of German requirements in Czech regions during the Habsburg Empire (Schjere, RR) [12], or attempts to recover proper English from the Americans (Mencken, 1919), or an attempt to disenfranchise Spanish speakers (Hall, Smith, Wicaksono). They are likely to be deliberate attempts to gain power, but they can also be well-intentioned efforts to alleviate real problems. Still, both problems seem to stem from a lack of perspective or awareness of different communities of practice with different linguistic needs or ever-changing needs.

The absence of a domain definition, or more accurately a Community of Practice definition, helps to highlight what language difficulty exists in the standards. A formal approach based on linguistics is required to define the community to which any standard belongs, and the body of experts responsible for developing that standard also needs to be evaluated.

Both components are necessary because there can be an open gap if the community of experts who set a standard does not accurately reflect the community it is intended to serve. This is one of the reasons why both are necessary. The inability to recognize that the two practitioners are from different communities and use a different language, as well as the fact that the discourse is focused on consent rather than acceptance and recognition of differences, may be the root causes of misunderstandings and conflicts that arise between them. This issue is common throughout the standards landscape. It is an inevitable consequence of the expert bias and experience bias inherent

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in the way SSOs are organized, the people who make up their members, and the people involved in the organization. This is not to be taken as an accusation, but as a simple observation of the way organizations generally perform their duties.

Language contains several features, five of which are most relevant to this discussion:

- 1) *Communities of Practice, or CoP for short, are groupings (including variations in dialect and jargon) characterized by a common culture (community), shared functions (purpose space), and shared procedures (practices), all resulting in a distinctive and distinctive language of their own .*
- 2) *Language is constantly changing and adapting, and its development is based on diversity and innovation.*
- 3) *There is no such thing as a "right" or "wrong" language.*
- 4) *Language has many different expressions, and according to Wittgenstein's theory of usage meaning, the meaning of a single word can change depending on how it is used and the context in which it is used.*
- 5) *The use of language is a product of social interaction and takes place within a social structure.*

is an essential component of incorporating standards . It is reasonable to assume that a member of any community intuitively understands the community to which he belongs and consequently does not consider it necessary to define that community when relating to other members of the same community. However, communities of practice are not mutually exclusive, and members may mistakenly assume that the target community is larger or smaller in the absence of effective dialogue.

It is possible that misunderstandings arise because of Communities of Practice existing as separate entities within the social system of a larger structure. The human body can be conceptualized as an overarching social structure that functions as a Community of Practice when viewed as a whole.

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However, each organ and system found in the human body resembles its own separate Community of Practice.

For example, the functions and processes that make up the gastrointestinal tract are quite different from those that define the brain. These differences can be seen quite easily. Despite working together to achieve the overarching goal of keeping the body functioning properly, they are still considered separate entities.

Literature review

As a result of expert bias, participants will mistakenly think that other participants have understood their statements in a certain way, rather than considering the possibility that their statements may have been misinterpreted due to translation from a different listener's perspective. It is possible that these misconceptions may not be detected until much later, so the basic assumptions on which any conclusion is built are likely to be wrong.

Even within the same language, the Vocational Community needs to be better defined in terms of jargon and dialect, as this will have an impact on how well people understand each other.

It is reasonable to anticipate that expert bias will play a more significant role in misunderstanding when dealing with much more complex ideas that require more expertise. As a result of expert bias, two experts from similar but different practice communities often assume that other experts agree with their views. If two experts in the field of "financial services" talk about "payments," one specializing in retail and consumer-type payments and the other specializing in corporate payments, their needs and goals will be quite different. Similarly, pediatricians and oncologists, both considered professionals in the medical field, have quite different specialties and needs; therefore, any specific requirements for one CoP will likely be less helpful to the other. It must be stressed, however, that the CoP-specific standard offers excellent value for the CoP for which it was designed.

The language change phenomenon is the language component responsible for creating friction between CoPs. Even with a broader social system in place, the language used in component communities of practice (CoPs) will continue to evolve and change regardless of the larger social

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system to which they belong. Even if an unspoken agreement is reached in the standardization process, this can lead to the formation of "common" standards in the standardization process that are not functional enough for many CoPs in the long run . This is the case even if tacit agreement is reached.

The adaptive function occurs when a speaker accepts a second speaker's statement, even if it doesn't seem natural to him, and then continues to use the other speaker's language in a way that allows communication between the two parties. In this way, people 'harmonize' by translating a language that is not their native language. Both accounts of the two features of discourse are rather primitive; nonetheless, they are useful for looking without delving too deeply into linguistic disparities that exist among communities of practice (Austin, 1962).

linguistics , is relevant to the issue of language variability between communities , as the community of practice itself is one of the contributors to providing context and intent within meaning. When speaking of a ' trade' from the perspective of a front office community (trader on the stock market) in the financial services world , context refers to the execution that takes place on an exchange. Currently, the meaning of the word "trade" in the context of a community of operations would refer to a transaction that is being closed at a local custodian. These are two separate things with only the least conceptual connection with each other, as will be shown in more detail in the following paragraphs. So, the norm produced is an agreement on an interpretation that is not objectionable for both CoPs ; however, in most cases this comment fails to capture the intricacies of either CoP . The meaning of "accepted" is not related to the actual linguistic meaning of any CoP , so its value will be reduced. In other words, "consensus is nothing but agreement." It does not give any guarantee that the information is accurate, dependable or even applicable. If reaching an agreement is prioritized over reaching a conclusion, it is only a legitimate method of decision making".

When trying to find solutions to difficult issues, reaching consensus is sometimes a fruitless effort as it hinders consideration of other options and perspectives. Professor Len from Harvard Business School According to Schlesinger , "They start to converge very quickly," which is one of the most

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negative by-products of the largely consensus model. Therefore, the consensus-based model is only suitable for the simplest, best-structured decisions.

Unless further clarification is provided, the consensus interpretation will not relate to the role or procedures of any CoP . Any further CoP- specific improvement added to the accepted definition will immediately affect the original agreed meaning. This will result in wording that once again differs between CoPs , invalidating the standard itself .

For example, two financial services professionals working on a data definition standard to define "trade" concluded that "trade is the exchange of one asset for another asset between two parties." Still, experts are part of two separate Community of Practices (CoPs), such as front office and customs clearance operations in the example presented earlier.

The data standard is the language used within the front office to discuss the executions that take place in an exchange. The concept of the front office application community (CoP) changes to consider that there is now a trade-off before the standard can be used. However, the term "trade" has a specific meaning in the context of barter transactions. This meaning refers to the transaction that takes place when an investment manager buys a stake in an asset. Therefore, barter COI does not include barter as one of its aspects; instead, it makes compliance with general market judgment a necessity. While the standard may seem to describe the same thing—that is, a transaction in which an item is bought and sold between two parties—in practice the two situations are fundamentally different and are not interchangeable. As a result, the solution proposed by the standard to a problem can only be effective for a limited time before the CoPs naturally begin to resegment. "Issues are never really addressed because situations around them are constantly changing".

There is a clear distinction between the function in which it is used, and the procedures applied when using the definition (context) . The standard definition lacks the sophistication that expert knowledge provides, so it does not in itself give any value in terms of meeting any need or demand. The descriptive language used within each CoP evolves and differentiates according to the needs and requirements of the context, but no change is made to the original standard. When a third CoP

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such as the Regulator steps in and expects to use the "trade" standard as a requirement for those that need to be reported, it can add an additional layer of complexity to the situation.

Because the dictionary does not contain context or ensemble as classifiers, listeners are left to experiment and discern which definition is being conveyed in any given speech.

This brings up an important aspect of language, which is that there is no such thing as a "right" or a "wrong" language. Both definitions, which are specific to their respective CoPs, are correct. To facilitate enhanced communication between standards and CoPs, both definitions need to be standardized in a way specific to each CoP. This will also ensure attribution of appropriate context within the community. Since the meaning of anything can change depending on who and where it is used, each specific norm needs to be defined in more detail in a written statement of the Code of Practice to which it is expressly concerned. As a result, the capacity to create a standard method that can translate between definitions and discover many of the subtleties and missing pieces necessary to successfully resolve conflict and give clear meaning becomes possible. As a result, when the third Community of Apps joins, they can correctly interpret various meanings depending on the context specified within each Community of Apps. The aim is to enable correct understanding during communication between Communities of Practice (CoPs) while maintaining the functionality required in each CoP.

of CoPs in Standards

This does not mean that all standards in force without proper attribution from the CoP are somehow problematic. The ambiguity caused by language and communities of practice will naturally diminish in standards for the real thing. Still, all standards will provide greater value and clarity if the process of clearly identifying the target CoP to which each standard should apply is conducted. This will be the case no matter what standard is considered. Where more than one CoP is defined, this will draw attention to the situations in which adjustments are made and indicate that additional work may be required to define the standard more precisely to account for differences in interpretation that could lead to different results. applications depending on the CoP. It is therefore possible for us to derive two different - but comparable - standards that are both more informative and practical.

Findings

A barrier to standards often presents itself later, not in the standardization process. When there is a standard, there are two possible dangers that can arise. The first reason is that the experts who developed the standard and the standard setter want to expand the field of application beyond what was originally intended. Second, when looking for a solution, it's common practice to choose a standard that seems "close enough". This is done on the assumption that alternatives (creating a new solution or validating existing workarounds) are more difficult to achieve or do not have the political support that a solution labeled "official standard" carries.

Using the term "standard" without any definition of what or for whom the standard is would be at least largely responsible for the source of the problem. According to generally agreed-upon definitions, a "standard" is anything that is "routinely and extensively used", "something established as a model", and "a measure of excellence". Therefore, it is assumed that choosing a "standard" will result in less friction or opposition to the decision, and the burden of proof falls on those who oppose the chosen standard.

The difficulty of successfully implementing standards, particularly those centered on interoperability, is not a new phenomenon. Egyedi and Dahanayake make a tentative reference to the issue of having multiple Enforcement Committees as a problem in their article "The Challenges of Enforcing Standards ." "The ideal of democratic, consensus decision-making demands more or less political concessions in committee standardization." This may result in a standard with multiple possibilities, or it may result in the deliberate use of vague language in the formulation of a standard so that opposing groups can rally around it. To date, not much research has been done to explore the problems arising from the adoption of standards or the potential for developing innovative approaches that will result in greater value and use.

On the other hand, if we accept standards as an expression of language, it may be a way to arrive at a formal, though still subjective, technique for researching, evaluating and producing standards through the lens of applied linguistics. In the realm of human language, political power has historically been exercised through the control and imposition of language, and this trend continues today. This is consistent with problems seen in the standards world.

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There are several conflicting purposes. For many people, there is an ardent desire to simplify difficult issues without breaking them down first. In any standardization process, political agendas with the potential to dominate people or businesses can be resolved using a consensus-based, quasi-democratic decision-making system. In the collective decision-making process, when there are several experts involved, difficulties may arise because of the need to work together and communicate among various groups that have different goals but need to work together within the wider social system. As a result, organizations responsible for standards development want to be relevant by ensuring that their standards are widely disseminated and used, whether they are appropriate based on a formal use case study.

The appearance of uniformity is produced using several different facades. However, this approach misses the fact that non-speakers will still need to translate standard documents into their native language. With no implementation concerns or no clear definition of the community for which the standard is targeted, it has become widespread practice to use standards as a solution to problems for which they were never designed. The result of this is that the standard is misunderstood, and the solution does not fit the purpose of the standard. As a result, the standard breaks down and moves away from its intended definition and purpose.

Standards undoubtedly provide significant value to the global community and lay the groundwork for the accelerated development of both knowledge and technology. However, in the search for standards, an extremely crucial step, such as identifying the community to which the standard belongs, as well as the specific use and application of the standard, is overlooked.

Argument

While diversity is a priority, this should not be done at the expense of giving greater power to those who do not know about the community for which the standard is intended. Nor should one group expect another community to define them. Participation and dialogue are necessary to understand the perspectives of other groups before any standards can be developed. A broad categorization serves no purpose other than to ignore critical nuances, and this results in a lack of rigor when it comes to uncovering fundamental misunderstandings or disparities in views.

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To be honest, there isn't much written about why we're having these challenges with standards. We can blame primary agents by looking at behavior, culture, and humanistic tendencies such as politics; These are all things that are not evaluated in the standards. Many SSOs have rules and processes that strive to mitigate the effects of these factors, but they are not directly geared towards recognizing or correcting problems.

In addition, there is always someone who will discover a "better" way to achieve something, which will eventually result in the establishment of a new norm. If there is no complete consensus that this new standard should be followed and the others abandoned, deviation will occur, as will the language itself.

most of the newly created standards that offer a better solution also offer a better solution for a particular group. However, if this is not formally recorded, properly defined, and continually reviewed and revised, the "problem" of having more than one standard "for the same thing" will continue to be an issue, the standards will be misused and deviated from their primary purpose and control policies, will continue to be enforced through the endorsement and abuse of standards.

The use of a technique based on applied linguistics has the potential to provide a great boost to the standards process. Clearly identifying and documenting the CoPs involved in the development of a standard not only provides clarity for subsequent implementation and use case , but can also formally reveal potential political, cultural and behavioral conflicts through an agnostic process. Clarity is achieved by doing these two things . Formal identification of the community of practice (or communities of practice) the standard is intended to serve may also reveal areas where there may be a lack of knowledge or counter-expert bias.

The goal is to provide a method, through applied linguistics, to understand and solve ostensibly duplicate standards-related problems, avoid standards misapplication and "scope drift", and create a better overall development process through a formal definition of community, context, and usage.

The primary focus of this academic article is to present various theoretical ideas from an academic perspective. Nevertheless, we believe it is important to provide a three-page description of the

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context and background of my educational setting. This should include an explanation of what first sparked my interest in academic literacy. At its core, not only has students' interests been blatantly ignored, but our strategy for teaching academic writing is built on a limited understanding of the barriers students face in their writing processes. This does not mean that we as university faculty do not have a broad understanding of the challenges students face in learning to develop an academic discourse. However, if this awareness is supported by a better understanding of the intrinsic challenges students face in the writing process – challenges that cannot be clearly identified in students' work – this can lead to potentially informed, contextually positioned and educational.

Also, when we were "teaching" students to think critically - because we all perceive academic writing to be inextricably linked with critical thinking - we did not consider several key issues, including the following. :

(a) How we understood the script; As a process, as a product, or both?

Since our teaching included activities, such as creating outlines, a product produced in the pre-writing stage , why did our assessment focus only on the final output?

What are the students' views on the academic writing first and our evaluation criteria second ?

(d) To what extent did the way we evaluate students' finished products assisted or hindered their evolving writing process?

(e) How much of a motivational impact did it have on students because of its focus on culture?

Anglo -American academic writing style characterized by a linear rhetorical structure and principles (such as consistency, coherence, conciseness, and textual simplicity) interpreted through a Western lens . This academic writing style is central to the academic writing model we teach, so it was important to us that our students learn about it. This model is described as "...it is both necessary and desirable for non-native English speakers to learn to compose texts according to the paradigms commonly found in Anglo -American writing if they are to participate in and contribute

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to the scientific and scientific knowledge repository ". technological knowledge" (both necessary and desirable for non-native English speakers to learn to compose text according to the paradigms commonly found in Anglo -American writing) (Swales and Feak , 1994 in Kachru , 1999, p.7)

Educators have a significant amount of power in many diverse types of schools. According to Freire (1970), this type of teaching is called the banker education model. According to this model, the task of the instructor is to convey a certain body of knowledge to the students. This body of knowledge is embedded in many second language composition programs and covers the social rules that govern writing in a Western academic discourse setting. If the purpose of students' participation in writing courses is to facilitate their transition to the academic discourse of Western institutions, then a transfer model is undoubtedly the best approach to follow. However, if the goal is not a one-way start but an awareness and validation of other intellectual traditions that may influence academic discourse, interactions in second language classrooms will need to change to accommodate this purpose (1993, pp. 76-77).

Therefore, instructional objectives need to be set very specifically. The style of training in which they are addressed is an additional challenge that needs to be addressed.

In essence, teaching paradigms are exported from countries in the core to those in the periphery. The inherent danger that comes with changing paradigms is explained by Guadilla (1987) as follows:

"The concept has been elaborated in one particular context and used in another, but this is not present in a particular culture of particular cultures of recent times."

Therefore, teaching models need to consider the cultural nuances of their students as well as the characteristics of the environment in which they are learning.

Rationale and Importance in the Field of Education

The research aims to gain a deeper understanding of the cultural characteristics of the learners and the specific contextual features in which this development takes place. As a result of trends in globalization and the increase in communication, which is more mediated by technology that transcends geographical boundaries, second language writing has become "an important, if not

dominant, subject of study in second language research" (Silva and Brice, 2004 , p . 7) . According to Silva and Brice's hypothesis, "the study of second language writing has become a respectable research topic in its own right" (2004, p. 7). To be more specific and blunter, what justifies expanding my knowledge of academic writing education through this article is that I continue to teach academic writing in Colombia – this time to English teachers who are teaching English in private schools. This is what justifies expanding my knowledge of academic writing training. It could be thought that teachers of English as a second language would have a strong command of the language in an academic setting . On the other hand, they seem comparable to the challenges faced by my undergraduates. Therefore, I believe that conducting research on the challenges Colombian students (both undergraduate and graduate) face in developing AAS- based academic literacy will enable me to approach the teaching of academic writing from a contextually placed perspective. This is a requirement (and a moral obligation) that I owe to my Colombian students, my profession, and myself. We also believe that this will lead me to improve my academic writing teaching.

What Exactly Is Meant By "Academic Writing"?

Simply put, academic writing is a form of communication specific to a particular community. It is a form primarily produced by members of the academic community for other members of the academic community. It is distinguished from other literary genres by its distinctive features, sometimes known as rules. In this section, we have focused on these features, or rules, to understand the myriad factors that combine to form the defining features of academic writing.

Morphology and Grammar Structure

Scarcella and Rumberger argue that a higher level of grammatical and morphological clarity is required for academic writing (2000). This academic written discourse is in stark contrast to the communication that takes place through speech: previous written discourse is predominantly an individual activity, especially the forming phase where ideas are put on paper which reduces the possibility of direct social interaction and feedback with the interlocutor. Speech, on the other hand, allows for repetition, backtracking, and expansion, somewhat constrained by the interlocutor's reaction to the spoken word and the degree of understanding. As a result of the absence of these linguistic elements in written communication, the author must maintain open

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channels of communication by making a deliberate choice of vocabulary, sentence structure and connecting tools. All these factors contribute to the successful transmission of "messages".

Conclusion

It is not surprising to find students whose language skills show a classic disconnect between strong oral proficiency and weaker academic writing skills, or vice versa. This is because academic discourse and speech are fundamentally different in nature, so it is not surprising to find students whose language skills prove this disconnect. To give an example, Generation 1.5 students are an example of the first generation, many of which are placed in separate departments at a certain level: the classroom is divided into two, where students who are perceived to be more advanced in writing and reading are placed. Those who see themselves as incompetent in writing and reading have students' characteristics of both first- and second-generation immigrants (Harklau , Siegal , & Losey , 1999): This illustrates the importance of writing skills in determining academic placement. This, too, has important implications for how these children are evaluated by the academic community, as they are often viewed as less gifted students than the typical student. In addition, there is a possibility that this may negatively affect the development of the student's identity, i.e., how the student sees himself/herself as both a person and a student. Despite this , research studies have shown that to develop academic literacy skills in an acceptable way, it is necessary to have a language foundation, i.e., a properly comprehensive vocabulary foundation alongside grammar and syntactic structures. According to Myles , "... in a fundamental sense, language proficiency and proficiency underlie the capacity to write in a second language.

As a result, teachers of second language writing should consider the development of both strategy and language skill when working with students" (2002, p.1). Simpson (1998), who argued that "they should have sufficient linguistic and general intellectual abilities to organize them into statements, paragraphs, and essays" (1998).

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